

A linguistic analysis of grammatical cohesion devices in discussion sections of undergraduate theses

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This study aims (a) to identify the types of grammatical cohesion used in the discussion sections of undergraduate theses and (b) to quantify the usage of these cohesive devices by EFL students in Aceh, Indonesia. Data were collected using an analytical sheet to identify instances of grammatical cohesion. The analysis revealed three types of grammatical cohesion in the discussion sections, with a total of 561 cohesive devices identified. The theses demonstrate a strong dependence on conjunctions (48.66%) and references (42.78%). Meanwhile, substitution is employed less often (8.56%), and ellipsis is entirely absent. Conjunctions and reference were the most frequently used due to their role in linking ideas and maintaining coherence, whereas substitutions were the least used because they are less effective for connecting larger segments of text. The findings of this study highlight students' understanding of the importance of grammatical cohesion as it helps ensure logical and clear sentence flow in academic writing.

Keywords: Academic Writing; Discussion Subgenre; Grammatical Cohesion; Undergraduate Thesis

1. Introduction

In linguistics, language signs are basically analyzed at four distinct levels: phonology, morphology, syntax, and semantics (Kracht, 2007); nevertheless, some scholars conduct linguistic analysis at the levels of (a) orthography (e.g., Bisson, 2023; Honkanen, 2023), (b) pragmatics (e.g., Salmani Nodoushan, 2019, 2021, 2022), (c) discourse (e.g., Prandi, 2023; Cerutti et al., 2023; Degano, 2023; Garzone, 2023; Iori, 2023), (d) society (e.g., Salmani Nodoushan, 2024), and so forth. As part of syntax, cohesion is a crucial element in effective writing, as it facilitates the flow of ideas and strengthens connections between phrases. Cohesion involves the semantic and grammatical relationships within

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a text (Salmani Nodoushan, 2007) that enhance its overall coherence and unity, including both grammatical ties (such as reference, ellipsis, substitution, and conjunctions) and lexical ties (like reiteration and collocation) (Ali, 2021; Jassim, 2023). Cohesive devices, including terms and phrases that connect sentences and paragraphs, are essential for producing a coherent flow of ideas (Zemach & Rumisek, 2003). These devices help readers recognize the topic under discussion and understand how various elements of the text relate to one another (Harmer, 2004). In well-structured writing, paragraphs should maintain internal coherence, with logical sentence order and smooth transitions (Birjandi et al., 2004; Boardman & Frydenberg, 2008).

Cohesion can be broadly categorized into two main types: lexical, and grammatical cohesion (Afrianto, 2017). Lexical cohesion focuses on semantic links between items in speech, whereas grammatical cohesion concerns structural connections between sentences and paragraphs. Grammatical cohesive devices include (a) reference, (b) substitution, (c) ellipsis, and (d) conjunction (Amperawaty & Warsono, 2019). The role of grammatical cohesion in academic writing, especially in theses and dissertations, is critical as it enhances the readability and comprehensibility of complex academic texts, allowing readers to follow the author's arguments more easily.

Although several studies have examined grammatical cohesion in various contexts, such as short stories (Sari, 2016) and student writings (Afrianto, 2017; Maulida et al., 2018; Prasetyaningrum et al., 2022), there is a notable gap in research specifically focusing on the discussion sections of undergraduate theses. The discussion section is a pivotal component of academic writing where students interpret their findings, compare them with existing literature, and draw conclusions (Salmani Nodoushan, 2011, 2012, 2023). Understanding how grammatical cohesion functions in this section could provide valuable insights for improving academic writing instruction and thesis preparation. This study aims to address this gap by analyzing grammatical cohesion specifically in the discussion sections of undergraduate theses written by students majoring in English at Universitas Syiah Kuala, Banda Aceh, Indonesia. By focusing on this particular section and population, the research seeks to provide better understanding of how grammatical cohesion is employed in a critical part of academic writing.

The study employed a systematic approach to identify and classify the types of grammatical cohesion used in the discussion sections. Drawing on the citation model from Turmudi (2020), the study quantified the occurrence of various cohesive elements, providing both a qualitative and quantitative analysis of grammatical cohesion in this context. Therefore, by conducting this focused analysis, the study aims to contribute to the broader understanding of grammatical cohesion in academic writing and potentially inform pedagogical

approaches to teaching cohesion in thesis writing for undergraduate students in English Education programs. Consequently, the research question for this study is:

- How is grammatical cohesion utilized in the discussion sections of undergraduate theses written by students majoring in English at Universitas Syiah Kuala?

2. Background

Academic writing is a nuanced skill that requires the mastery of many things including syntax, semantics, rhetorical organization, text development, genres, rhetorical moves, avoidance of logical fallacies, cohesion, coherence, etc. (Johns & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015; Khakbaz & Salmani Nodoushan, 2011; Montazeran & Salmani Nodoushan, 2012; Salmani Nodoushan, 2007a, 2007b, 2007c, 2007d, 2009, 2011a, 2011b, 2012, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2018). Cohesion, defined as the 'grammatical' and 'lexical' patterns of lexis in text that holds the text together and gives it meaning and texture, is considered to be related to the concept of coherence (Halliday & Hasan, 1976; Hoey, 1991).

Cohesion occurs when elements within a discourse are interdependent, with one element reinforcing another (Nirwanto, 2021). It can be understood that cohesion strengthens the connection between these elements. Semantics, as the foundational concept, relates to the way meaning is connected within a text (Gao et al., 2017). In any text, cohesion functions as the link that connects sentences, ensuring grammatical coherence and meaning. Moeliono (2017) asserts that to achieve a well-structured and complete discourse, sentences must be cohesively tied together. Without such cohesion, the relationships between discourse elements cannot be interpreted according to their reliance on one another. Cohesion allows the establishment of semantic relationships within the discourse and guarantees coherence.

Grammatical cohesion, a form of cohesion that works in tandem with lexical cohesion to create texture, refers to the use of grammar to achieve cohesion within a text. It involves employing devices that connect words, phrases, clauses, and sentences. These connectors establish relationships among different parts of a text, ensuring continuity. Conjunctions, ellipses, references, and substitutions are the four main types of grammatical cohesive devices (Amperawaty & Warsono, 2019). University students need to understand the various types and functions of these devices, as they help link sentences and paragraphs structurally, ensuring that the ideas permeating them remain consistent. These devices are to be effectively used in both written and spoken discourse (Anwar, 2017).

According to Wahyuni and Oktaviani (2021), grammatical cohesion is marked by specific grammatical devices that connect elements across sentence boundaries. These features are essential for the understanding of the interconnectedness and integration of a text. Muttaqin et al. (2021) argue that grammatical cohesion is necessary in all text genres because it links paragraphs, allowing for continuity and a coherent flow of ideas. This grammatical integration enhances the reader's comprehension of the author's work, whereas a lack of grammatical cohesion can lead to confusion. Therefore, as Emilia et al. (2018) suggest, college students should grasp the concepts of both coherence and grammatical cohesion, which are a crucial aspect of overall cohesion.

Grammatical cohesion within a text is achieved through the use of four primary types of cohesive devices: (a) conjunctions, (b) ellipses, (c) references, and (d) substitutions (Amperawaty & Warsono, 2019). Halliday and Hasan (2013) state that conjunctions deal with different types of semantic relations, one which is no longer any kind of a search instruction but a specification of how what is to flow systematically connected to what has gone before. It is classified into four types: (a) additive conjunction, (b) adversative conjunction, (c) clausal conjunction, and (d) temporal conjunction. Likewise, Schiffrin et al. (2001), noted that conjunction is concerned with resources for connecting messages, via (a) addition, (b) comparison, (c) temporality, and (d) causality. Martin and Rose (2007) also grouped conjunctions into the four categories proposed by Halliday and Hasan (2013) but stated that they may occur as internal and/or external conjunctions.

According to Bahaziq (2016), ellipsis is a grammatical cohesion in the form of the so-called 'constituents'. A perceivable sentence element known as an ellipsis is not stated clearly in the following sentence. The presence of the components of the sentence can be estimated even though they are not stated in writing. Ellipsis indicates continuity; allowing speaker and addressee to focus on what is contrastive (Halliday & Mathiessen, 2014). Halliday and Hasan (2013) classified ellipsis into three types: (a) nominal ellipsis, (b) verbal ellipsis, and (c) clausal ellipsis.

Reference is a linguistic element used in discourse to refer to something or someone (Bloor & Bloor, 2004). It occurs when one word refers to another within the discourse. Kushartanti et al. (2005) categorize references into three types: (a) personal, (b) demonstrative, and (c) comparative. Personal reference refers to the person category that is used to follow names, things, or objects that are referred to further in the text (Halliday & Hassan, 2013). The category of personals includes three classes: (a) personal pronouns, (b) possessive determiners (usually called possessive adjective), and (c) possessive pronouns (Hameed, 2008). Meanwhile, demonstratives are those items that refer to their

referents by indicating their location on the proximity scale, as opposed to personal reference items, which refer to their referents by describing their function in the speech situation (Hameed, 2008). Halliday and Hasan (2013) recognize two types of demonstrative references: (a) adverbial demonstratives that express the location of a process in space or time (such as 'here', 'there', 'now', and 'then'), and (b) selective nominal demonstratives (i.e., this, these, that, those) along with the definite article 'the'. Comparative reference materials function in both nominal and adverbial groups, and comparisons are made either in terms of specific characteristics of quantity and quality or in terms of more common characteristics of identity, similarity, and difference (Halliday & Hasan, 2013).

Lastly, substitution is used where a speaker or writer wishes to avoid the repetition of a lexical item and can draw on the grammatical resources of the language to replace the item (Bloor & Bloor, 2004). According to Bahaziq (2016), substitution is the process of changing one thing in a text to another in order to avoid duplication. There are three types of substitution: (a) nominal (one, ones, same), (b) verbal (do), and (c) clausal (so, not).

3. Method

For this study, a descriptive qualitative research design (cf. Sandelowski, 2000) was chosen, as it allows for an in-depth examination of cohesive devices in undergraduate thesis discussions; the findings are presented descriptively. Qualitative research aims to reveal understandings that cannot be captured through numerical or measurable processes, focusing instead on obtaining detailed information from diverse perspectives (Mistry, 2012).

3.1. Participants

This study focused on three undergraduate theses, so there were three participants. The subject was the discussion sections written by undergraduate students majoring in English at Universitas Syiah Kuala, Banda Aceh. The discussion section was selected due to its potential to demonstrate the student's ability to use language cohesively, particularly in academic writing. The object of analysis was the grammatical cohesion devices used within the discussion section of theses. Concentrating on this specific text allowed for a thorough analysis of the linguistic strategies employed to maintain clarity, texture, and structure in academic discourse.

3.2. Materials

The researchers utilized an analytical sheet as the primary instrument for data collection. This sheet is also known as 'spreadsheet'; they are commonly employed for data collection because of their ease of use and analytical features

(Nurdiantoro et al., 2017). This tool was employed to analyze the discussion section of the three selected undergraduate theses. The analysis focused on identifying and categorizing grammatical cohesive devices, specifically (a) reference, (b) substitution, (c) conjunction, and (d) ellipsis. The sheet enabled the researchers to evaluate how these cohesive elements contribute to the overall coherence and flow of the thesis discussion, ensuring a comprehensive and precise analysis of grammatical cohesion in the text.

3.3. Procedure

To collect the necessary data, the researchers selected three undergraduate theses written by three English students. The researchers then carefully read the discussion section of each thesis. Subsequently, the discussion sections were analyzed to identify and document instances of grammatical cohesion. Informed by Creswell and Poth's (2018) qualitative research framework, the procedure included: (1) listing all instances of grammatical cohesion found in the text, (2) organizing these instances into a table by types of grammatical cohesion, and (3) calculating the frequency of each type of cohesive device and describing the results.

4. Results

This study aimed to analyze the use of grammatical cohesion in the discussion sections of undergraduate theses, focusing on four categories: reference, substitution, conjunction, and ellipsis. The analysis of these discussion sections revealed the distribution of grammatical cohesion types, as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1

Types of Grammatical Cohesion Used in the Discussion Part of Theses

No	Type of Grammatical Cohesion	Occurrences	Percentage
1.	Conjunction	273	48.66%
2.	Reference	240	42.78%
3.	Substitution	48	8.56%
4.	Ellipsis	0	0%
Total		561	100%

Table 1 shows that, out of the 561 instances of grammatical cohesion identified in the discussion sections of theses, conjunctions are the most prevalent, accounting for 48.66% of the occurrences. References follow with 42.78%, while substitutions appear much less frequently at 8.56%, and ellipses are absent. The data indicates that conjunctions are the most frequently utilized form of grammatical cohesion, whereas substitutions are notably less common.

As stated before, a conjunction is a connection (or cohesive tie) that indicates how the subsequent sentence or clause should be connected to the preceding parts of the sentence. Halliday and Hasan (2013) classify conjunctions into four types: additive, causal, temporal, and adversative.

Table 2

Categories of Conjunction Used in the Discussion Part of Theses

No.	Categories of Grammatical Cohesion	Occurrences
1.	Additive conjunction	99
2.	Causal conjunction	72
3.	Temporal conjunction	57
4.	Adversative conjunction	45
Total		273

Table 2 categorizes the conjunctions observed in the theses discussions according to their types. Additive conjunctions are the most frequently used, with 99 occurrences, followed by causal conjunctions with 72 occurrences, temporal conjunctions with 57, and adversative conjunctions with 45. Additive conjunctions, such as 'and' which appears 99 times, are used to connect additional information or ideas.

Example 1: It is important to note that this occurred only in select cases **and** not throughout the entirety of the data.

In Example 1, the word 'and' functions as an additive conjunction, linking two pieces of related information. It adds more information while maintaining the relationship between the ideas.

Example 2: This technique was chosen **because** of the similarities in grammatical structures between the source language (SL) and the target language (TL).

In Example 2, 'because' functions as a causal conjunction, explaining the reason or cause behind the choice of the technique. It links the action ("was chosen") to the reason for that action ("similarities in grammatical structures").

Example 3: The transposition technique is also employed **when** translating adjective words.

In Example 3, 'when' connects two parts of the sentence by introducing a temporal or conditional relationship between them. It links the action "is also employed" with the condition or specific situation in which it happens

("translating adjective words"). Here, this cohesive device clarifies the circumstances under which the transposition technique is applied, contributing to the flow and understanding of the sentence.

Example 4: The reduction technique shares similarities with linguistic compression, **but** with a slight difference.

In Example 4, the use of the word 'but' as the adversative conjunction is for a contrast or opposition between the reduction technique and linguistic compression, highlighting that while they are similar, there is a notable distinction between them.

Unlike conjunction, reference relates words to their objects or meanings within the text. It includes demonstrative, personal, and comparative references.

Table 3
Categories of Reference Used in the Discussion Part of Theses

No.	Categories of Grammatical Cohesion	Occurrences
1.	Demonstrative reference	120
2.	Personal reference	114
3.	Comparative reference	6
Total		240

Table 3 summarizes the occurrences of three different types of references. Demonstrative references are the most common, with 120 occurrences, followed by personal references with 114, and comparative references with only 6 occurrences. The total number of references across all three categories is 80.

Example 5: **This** approach aids the comprehension of the content for the target audience, as it sounds more natural in the target language.

In Example 5, the word "this" is a demonstrative reference pointing back to a previously mentioned approach. It creates cohesion by linking the current sentence to earlier information in the text.

Example 6: Based on the data findings, **it** was observed that the translator frequently applied this technique.

In Example 6, the pronoun "it" is a personal reference that likely refers to a subject previously mentioned in the text (such as a study, analysis, or report).

It prevents the repetition of the noun and maintains continuity with earlier sentences.

Example 7: In this technique, additional information is included in the translation to provide a **better** understanding of the context for the target audience.

In Example 7, the word 'better' is comparative reference that compares the understanding of the context provided by the additional information in the translation to a previous level of understanding, suggesting an improvement.

By way of contrast, substitution involves replacing one element with another. The data reveals that substitution is less frequently used, accounting for only 8.56% of the total grammatical cohesion.

Table 4

Categories of Substitution Used in the Discussion Part of the Theses

No.	Categories of Grammatical Cohesion	Occurrences
1.	Causal substitution	33
2.	Verbal conjunction	15
Total		48

Table 4 presents the data on various substitution devices within the text. Causal substitution appears 33 times, indicating its frequent use to replace one element with another, establishing cause-and-effect relationships. Verbal conjunction occurs 15 times, highlighting its role in connecting clauses or sentences through verbal links. These devices account for a total of 48 occurrences, underlining their combined contribution to maintaining coherence and cohesion in the text.

Example 8: However, unlike Maha's research, this study **did not** find any data that fulfilled the specifications of the discursive creation technique.

In Example 8, the word 'not' is used as a causal substitution in 'did not find' to imply that the absence of finding data is the result or outcome of the study's observations, contrasting with what was found in Maha's research.

Example 9: The researcher noticed that in some cases the translator **did** include Indonesian conjunction words to enhance the completeness and natural flow of the translation.

In Example 9, verbal substitution involves using a form of a verb to avoid repeating an earlier action or verb phrase. In this sentence, the auxiliary verb 'did' is used before 'include' to emphasize that the action indeed took place. The word 'did' replaces the need to repeat the full verb phrase from an earlier context. For example, if the text had previously mentioned that the translator typically includes conjunctions, the sentence could use 'did' to avoid restating "includes."

Finally, ellipsis omits elements that are understood from the context. As table 1 shows, ellipsis was not found in the discussion sections of the theses under evaluation.

5. Discussion

The most prominent cohesive device category identified in this study was 'conjunctions', which make up 48.66% of all grammatical cohesion devices. This result is consistent with previous research, such as Afrianto (2017) and Prasetyaningrum et al. (2022), who also found conjunctions to be the most frequently used cohesive device in student writing. However, the percentage in this study is notably higher, suggesting a reliance on conjunctions in thesis discussion sections.

The frequent use of conjunctions, particularly additive conjunctions (99 occurrences), indicates that students are adept at linking ideas and adding information. This is especially important in discussion sections, where connecting findings to existing literature and elaborating on interpretations is essential. However, the heavy dependence on conjunctions could also signal a lack of variety in cohesive strategies. While additive conjunctions were most prevalent, causal conjunctions (72 occurrences) and temporal conjunctions (57 occurrences) were also used extensively. This distribution differs from studies like Sari (2016), who observed a more balanced use of conjunction types in short stories. The higher occurrence of causal conjunctions in this study likely reflects the emphasis on cause-effect relationships and logical reasoning in thesis discussions.

References were the second most common type of cohesive devices, accounting for 42.78% of the total. This aligns with findings by Maulida et al. (2018) and Amperawaty & Warsono (2019), who also reported references as a significant cohesive device in academic writing. However, this study provides a more detailed breakdown of reference types. The predominance of demonstrative references (120 occurrences) over personal references (114 occurrences) is particularly notable. This contrasts with some earlier studies on student writing, where personal references were more common. The frequent use of demonstrative references in thesis discussions may suggest a more advanced approach to academic writing where students focus on

referring to abstract ideas and concepts rather than relying on personal pronouns. Meanwhile, the minimal use of comparative references (6 occurrences) is unexpected and contrasts with studies such as Emilia et al. (2018), which reported a higher frequency of comparative references in academic texts. This discrepancy may indicate an area for improvement, as comparative references can be useful for discussing research findings in relation to prior studies.

The limited use of substitution (8.56% of the total) and the complete absence of ellipsis are significant findings. This pattern diverges from other studies—e.g., Bahaziq (2016)—which found a broader use of these cohesive devices in academic writing. The scarcity of substitution and the lack of ellipsis may reflect a more explicit and direct writing style, perhaps driven by a focus on clarity in academic discourse. The discussion sections of the theses are formal and academic in nature and typically emphasize clarity, precision, and explicitness in presenting ideas. In academic discourse, writers often avoid omitting elements that could be implied, as this could lead to ambiguity or misunderstanding. Instead, they tend to provide complete and fully-formed sentences to ensure that all arguments and explanations are clearly articulated, leaving little room for the type of omission that ellipsis entails. However, despite this assumption, this raises questions about students' familiarity with these cohesive devices. The absence of ellipsis, in particular, could suggest missed opportunities to create more concise and sophisticated texts. As Halliday and Matthiessen (2014) argue, ellipsis can be a powerful tool for emphasizing contrastive elements in writing.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, the analysis of grammatical cohesion in the discussion sections of undergraduate theses highlights a predominant reliance on conjunctions (48.66%), which account for nearly half of all cohesive devices used. References also play a significant role, making up 42.78% of the total occurrences, while substitution (8.56%) is less frequently employed, and ellipsis is absent altogether. These findings suggest that students are proficient in using conjunctions and references to maintain textual cohesion, but may benefit from greater familiarity with other cohesive strategies such as substitution and ellipsis to enhance the sophistication and variety of their academic writing.

A limitation of this study is its focus on three theses written by EFL undergraduate students at just one university, which restricts the generalizability of the findings to a broader range of academic writing. The absence of ellipsis and the minimal use of substitution may also reflect the writing style of these three students only, rather than providing a

comprehensive view of how the cohesive devices used in undergraduate theses more broadly. For future research, a larger sample size that includes theses from different disciplines could offer a more representative analysis of grammatical cohesion. Additionally, further studies could explore why certain cohesive devices, such as ellipsis and substitution, are underutilized and could show how instruction on these devices may improve the clarity and sophistication of students' writing.

Authors' Statement

All authors affirm that they collaboratively developed and conceived the ideas presented in this paper. The first author was responsible for initiating the research concept and conducting the data collection. Meanwhile, the second and third authors played crucial roles in shaping the overall conception of the paper. The fourth author was involved in the editing and refining of the draft.

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